

1 **Combined growth factor inhibition in CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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8 1. The protocol design described here includes an inhibitor targeting each of the growth factor
9 receptors whose activation and differential expression in CNS metastasis we discovered and described
10 (below):

- 11 i. EGFR (HER1)
 - 12 1. gefitinib
 - 13 2. erlotinib
- 14 ii. MET
 - 15 1. cabozantinib
 - 16 2. crizotinib
- 17 iii. ERBB2 (HER2)
 - 18 1. lapitinib
 - 19 2. neratinib

20 2. The combined growth factor targeting strategy here includes an antibody targeting vascular
21 endothelial growth factor-alpha, bevacizumab.
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1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: MET.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to distant sites in breast cancer, like
7 the central nervous system (CNS) and the lungs, is difficult to treat and heterogeneous in nature,
8 complicating its management (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the
9 full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in
10 metastasis to the CNS and metastasis to the lung (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies
11 (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the CNS metastases of humans with breast cancer. We identify
12 here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the
13 CNS in humans with breast cancer, MET, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of
14 CNS metastasis.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, “regional” metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the CNS to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the CNS metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: MET.

Results

Figure 1: MET is differentially expressed in CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. CNS metastases in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.

n=5 CNS metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4233	7.06E-03	0.986	-5.653817	2.673795	241.62	MET	759/22,997	96.7

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CNS metastases and lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *MET* in metastasis to the CNS in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of MET changed more than 96% of the human CNS metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the positive fold-change indicating increased quantity of MET messenger RNA in CNS metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of MET during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of MET likely defined the CNS metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of MET, immunoglobulin- or small molecule-based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with CNS metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

References

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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 (9) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in metastasis to the CNS (central nervous system) in humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 [10] for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: EGF.**

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n=5 CNS metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1950	4.12E-05	0.865	4.1005	3.547781	484.39	EGF	128/22,997	99.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CNS metastases and lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *EGF* in metastasis to the CNS in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of EGF changed more than 99% of the human CNS metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the positive fold-change indicating increased quantity of EGF messenger RNA in CNS metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of EGF during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

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